

Assessment of Principals' Commitment... (Sulyman, et. al., 2024) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15026553>

Assessment of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal among Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

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Abstract

The study assessed the principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal among public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. Descriptive research design of survey type was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all the 2,372 teachers in the 42 public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government in 2023/2024 academic session. Random sampling technique was used to select 21(50%) out of the 42 schools while 292 teachers were selected out of the 1,205 in the sampled schools, using proportionate sampling technique. Assessment of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal' (APCTPA) was used to collect data. Validity of the instrument was done and its reliability test yielded an index of 0.79. The findings of the study revealed that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low. Also, gender and years of experience did not cause any significant difference in the teachers' opinions on the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. It was recommended that school principals need to be more committed to performance appraisal by personally carrying it out and also charge Vice Principals (Academic), Heads of Department or any experienced teachers within or outside the schools to perform it, so as to improve teachers' job performance.

Key words: Assessment, Principals, Commitment, Teachers, Performance Appraisal

Introduction

Principals play important roles in secondary education and one of such is serving as human resource managers. As managers of human resource, it is their responsibility to ensure that performance of teachers is subjected to periodic appraisal, so as to enhance it and facilitate effective realisation of the school goals. Sunday (2021) stated that school principals need to pay adequate attention to how teachers perform their duties to be able to carry out appraisal on them, for the purpose of determining where they perform rightly and the areas where they perform below the established standard. Seniwoliba (2014), teachers' performance appraisal (PA) as a school principal's role is all-encompassing; it involves identifying, evaluating and developing teachers' work aptitude, so as to improve school performance. It is an imperative to attainment of organizational objectives, and benefits employees in terms of recognition, receiving feedback, catering to work needs, and offering career guidance.

According to Johnson (2018), performance appraisal (PA) is a method of measuring performance of workers in an organisation, so as to ensure that corrections are made where necessary, for the purpose of making their job performance enhance goal achievement. Alice and Oluoch (2019) and Unachukwu and Orji (2021) stated that PA refers to the act of assessing a teacher's performance. It fosters objective skill evaluation and adherence to the established rules. Obisi (2018) opined that PA of workers is an important aspect of human resource management and it is used in determining their career advancement

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and also facilitating their effective job performance. Musodza et al. (2020) emphasised that the reason for appraising employees' performance is not limited to enhancing their job satisfaction but also an avenue increasing their professional capacity building and dedication to duties. The finding of the study conducted by Looney (2017) revealed that that job appraisal is a significant way of improving teachers' job performance. Hence, government and principals need to ensure that it is properly carried out in public secondary schools in Nigeria. Mullins (2022) believed that the salient purpose of performance appraisal is to improve the discharge of duties of each worker, thereby resulting to increased output in the performance of the organisation as a whole. Fisher et al. (2018) opined that the role which performance appraisal plays in enhancing effective employees' job performance cannot be over-emphasised. If used properly, it could help in achieving the stated goals but if utilised inappropriately, it could have disastrous effects on employees.

Malik et al. (2021) stressed that the fundamental goal of appraising teachers' job performance is to assist in making their performance more effective. Ajayi (2021) posited that performance appraisal means the process of assessing the performance of employees in order to determine their training needs, for the purpose of assisting organisation to actualise its goals. Riyanto et al. (2021) emphasised that for the established goals to be achieved, educational enterprises need teachers who have good performance and as a result of this, managers need to periodically assess teachers' productivity through effective performance appraisal, so as to determine the areas where need to improve upon. Dal Corso et al., (2020) maintained that PA assists in facilitating good employees' performance, informs managers at the right time of the need for capacity building in certain areas, helps a poorly performing employees and creates compensation and promotion systems to enhance performance. Kareithi (2018) opined that results derived from PA could be used by managers of organisations to make important decisions on pay, retention, promotions, downsizing and termination of employees' appointment, if need arises.

Milimu et al. (2024) maintained that in educational institutions, PA is seen as a continuous process which is embarked upon, so as to detect, measure, and develop performance of teachers in accordance with the goals of Ministry of Education. Ayeni, (2018) stated that the act of appraising performance of employees usually entails formative aspects centering on capacity building, feedback, and performance, purposely focused on enhancing achievement and making quality educational experience available for students. Maxwell and Schwimmer (2016) stressed that performance appraisal of teachers is a duty of principals as school managers, which focuses on value judgment on how strong or weak a teacher's job performance is, using the gathered information to juxtaposes the real work performance with the established performance standards. Mollé et al. (2023) believed that the use of PA in the school system needs proper management, so as to prevent the possibility of wrongness which could lead to reduction in teachers' productivity. Singh and Singh (2020) maintained that PA is an aspect of human resource management which is used for making decisions on important issues relating to employees such as promotion, capacity building through training and retention in the organisation. Arimie and Orobosa (2023) emphasised that the process of appraising performance of workers has to be fair, highlighting clearly defined objectives, assessments, feedback for evaluated employees, and performance-boosting plans, so as to achieve overall productivity in organisation. Gbadamosi (2024) opined that performance appraisal is a method used by principals for improving outcomes and overseeing performance of teachers in schools. The purpose is to connect the school goals with the aspirations of each teacher aspirations, in order to make his or her performance conforms to the student academic needs.

Statement of the Research Problem

Principals as the general overseers of secondary schools stand in the position of personally appraising or ensuring that performance of teachers under them are appraised by some designated staff from within or outside the schools, for the purpose of determining their areas of strength and weakness, so that necessary professional actions could be taken to remedy the professional errors identified. However, observations of the researchers and information derived from teachers in some schools showed that some school principals, on daily basis, utilise virtually all official hours inside their offices without earmarking specific time to meet teachers in classrooms, for the purpose of appraising their job performance. Not only that, they seem not bother to charge vice principals (Academic), Heads of Departments or experienced teachers to perform same on their behalf, so as to improve teachers' job performance. This could hinder not only the realisation of effective teachers' job performance but also overall school goals.

Many studies which are related to this study had been conducted. To mention but few, Gbadamosi (2024) conducted a study on the use of performance appraisal and reward system in enhancing employee performance in secondary schools: A case study of public secondary schools in Delta State. Milimu et al. (2024) investigated the influence of teacher performance appraisal and development tool on job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools in Keiyo North Sub-County, Kenya. James and Olayiwola (2022) examined the impacts of performance appraisal on teachers' job performance in secondary

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schools in Kebbi State. Alarape (2020) carried out a study on the performance appraisal and teachers’ effectiveness in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. However, none of the study mentioned above specifically focused on assessment of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal among public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State; hence, this is the observed academic lacuna which this study was set out to fill.

Objectives of the study

The study:

1. examined the level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State;
2. investigated the difference in level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers’ gender; and
3. determined the difference in level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers’ years of experience; and

Research Questions

The following research question was raised.

1. What is the level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State?

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated in the study.

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers’ gender.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers’ years of experience.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design of survey type. All the 2,372 teachers in the 42 public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area constituted population of the study. Through the use of random sampling technique, 21 schools which represented 50% of the entire school population were selected. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 292 teachers out of the 1,205 teachers in the sampled schools, using Krejcie and Morgan table for sample size determination. A questionnaire designed by the researchers, titled ‘Assessment of Principals’ Commitment to Teachers’ Performance Appraisal’ (APCTPA) was used to collect data from the respondents. The questionnaire, which contained 10 items, was validated by three experts in the fields of Educational Management and Test and Measurement. This was done in order to ensure the face and content validity of the questionnaire. Through the use of split-half method, thirty copies of the questionnaire were administered to 30 teachers drawn from the schools which were not used in the study. The data gathered were analysed using Crobach’s Alpha and a reliability index of 0.79 was obtained. This confirmed suitability of the instrument for use in the study. Three of the researchers and two research assistants visited the sampled schools to administer questionnaire to the respondents. Each copy of the questionnaire was collected immediately after filling. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research question, t-test was used to test hypothesis one while Analysis of Variance was used to test hypothesis two. Any mean score not up to 2.50 was adjudged ‘Low’ while the mean score from 2.50 and above was considered ‘High’. Out of the 292 copies of the questionnaire distributed for administration, only 263 copies returned were used for analysis.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of principals’ commitment to teachers’ performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State?

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer research question one.

Table 1: Level of Principals’ Commitment to Teachers’ Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
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1.	educates teachers on the meaning and importance of performance appraisal, to be able to understand its benefits to them	2.39	.72	Low
2.	periodically conducts performance appraisal on teachers, for the purpose of detecting their areas of strength and weakness	2.26	.61	Low
3.	gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the performance appraisal carried out on them, for them to know the areas of their strengths and weaknesses	2.22	.45	Low
4.	delegates authority to the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department to periodically appraise your job performance on his or her behalf	2.64	.90	High
5.	ensures that the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the appraisal conducted on them	2.50	.66	High
6.	uses information derived from performance appraisal to make to make important decisions on teachers	1.51	.68	Low
7.	makes teachers to understand that performance appraisal is a way of assisting and motivating them for effective job performance	2.17	.40	Low
8.	within his or her capacity, provides professional support so as to improve the area(s) of weakness observed in teachers during performance appraisal	1.98	.57	Low
9.	recommends teachers for capacity building programme(s) based on the need(s) identified in them during performance appraisal	1.92	.43	Low
10.	possesses professional skills to effectively conduct performance appraisal for teachers	2.70	1.11	High
	Total	2.27	.65	Low

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 1 presented the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State. As shown on the table, items 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8 and 9 (educates teachers on the meaning and importance of performance appraisal, to be able to understand its benefits to them, periodically conducts performance appraisal on teachers, for the purpose of detecting their areas of strength and weakness, gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the performance appraisal carried out on them, for them to know the areas of their strengths and weaknesses, uses information derived from performance appraisal to make to make important decisions on teachers, makes teachers to understand that performance appraisal is a way of assisting and motivating them for effective job performance, within his or her capacity, provides professional support so as to improve the area(s) of weakness observed in teachers during performance appraisal and recommends teachers for capacity building programme(s) based on the need(s) identified in them during performance appraisal) had mean scores: 2.39, 2.26, 2.22, 1.51, 2.21, 1.98 and 1.92 respectively and such declared 'Low'. Also, item 4, 5 and 10 (delegates authority to the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department to periodically appraise your job performance on his or her behalf, ensures that the Vice Principal (Academic) or Head of your Department gives teachers feedback on the outcome of the appraisal conducted on them and possesses professional skills to effectively conduct performance appraisal for teachers) had mean scores: 2.64, 2.50 and 2.72; hence, adjudged 'High'. Therefore, with the mean score of 2.27, level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

T-test was used to test hypothesis one.

Table 2: T-test Showing the Difference in the Significant Difference in Level of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State Based on Teachers' Gender

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Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	119	2.14	.61	2.27	.066	Ho ₁ Accepted
Female	144	2.40	.79			

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 2 showed the calculated t-value (2.27), mean difference of 0.14 and the p-value (0.66) which is greater than the significance level (0.05). Hence, hypothesis two was rejected. This shows that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience.

Analysis of Variance was used to test hypothesis two.

Table 3: ANOVA Analysis Showing the Difference in the Significant Difference in Level of Principals' Commitment to Teachers' Performance Appraisal in Public Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State Based on Teachers' Years of Experience

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	Cal. F-ratio	p-value	Decision
Between Groups	13.224	3	.331	2.29	.065	Ho ₂ Accepted
Within Groups	16.117	260	.147			
Total	29.331	263				

Source: Field survey, 2024.

Table 3 shows the cal. F-ratio (2.29) and the p-value (.065) that is greater than the level of significance (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis two (Ho₂) was accepted. This shows that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was low. This finding agrees with the finding of James and Olayiwola (2022) which revealed that the level of principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in secondary schools in Kebbi State was low. This finding is also in tandem with the position of Johnson (2018) that many principals in public secondary school in Nigeria do not prioritise appraisal of teachers in their schools and this might be the reason for ineffective job performance of teachers.

The finding of the study showed that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' gender. This finding supports the finding of Alarape (2020) which showed that there was no significant difference in the opinions of male and female teachers on the principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State. This finding corroborates the finding of Sunday (2021) which showed that male and female teachers were not significantly different in their opinions on the commitment of principals to teachers' performance appraisal in Lagos State secondary schools.

The finding of the study showed that there was no significant difference in level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State based on teachers' years of experience. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Alarape (2020) which showed that there was no significant

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difference in the opinions of male and female teachers on the principals' dedication to performance appraisal of teachers in Kogi West Senatorial District, Kogi State.

Conclusion

The study concluded that level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State was declared low. Also, gender and years of experience did not cause any significant difference in the teachers' opinions on the level of principals' commitment to teachers' performance appraisal in public secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government, Kwara State.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

1. school principals need to be more committed to performance appraisal by personally carrying it out and also charge Vice Principals (Academic), Heads of Department or any experienced teachers within or outside the schools to perform it, so as to improve teachers' job performance;
2. there is need to ensure that teachers are given feedback on the performance appraisal carried out on them, for the purpose of knowing the areas of their strength and weakness and improve where necessary, so as to facilitate actualisation of the school goals; and
3. Ministry of Education should periodically organise capacity building for principals, so as to make them acquire more skills on how to properly appraise job performance of teachers, for the purpose of enhancing their performance and school goals.

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